

Supplementary Material

All datasets and supplementary materials are available from Dryad (<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.95x69p8sz>) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7509863>) associated public online repositories. Raw Illumina reads have been submitted to the Short Read Archive (SRA) of the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) and are available under BioProject number PRJNA949844. Digital 3D models of the *Dasypus guianensis* holotype specimen are freely available through MorphoMuseuM (<https://morphomuseum.com/specimenfiles/send-file-specimenfile/1200/4a65cc83>; <https://morphomuseum.com/specimenfiles/send-file-specimenfile/1201/7ed725a9>).

Supplementary Results

Further comparison with literature

We extracted the partial 16S rRNA sequences of the four individuals of *D. s. septemcinctus*, *D. hybridus*, *D. novemcinctus* from French Guiana, *D. mazzai* and *D. sabanicola* analyzed in Abba et al. (2018) and combined them with our three mitochondrial sequences obtained for *D. novemcinctus* individuals from Argentina, Uruguay and Paraguay. *D. novemcinctus* individuals from Argentina, Uruguay, and Paraguay did not cluster with the reference mitogenome of *D. novemcinctus* from French Guiana but rather with *D. mazzai* and *D. sabanicola* (Fig. S18).

We also analyzed the partial D-loop sequences of 221 individuals from Arteaga et al. (2020) with the corresponding D-loop sequences extracted from our 19 individuals in common, allowing for direct sequence comparisons (Table S4). We found 13 individuals with incongruent sequences (Table S4). These South American individuals were all assigned to the Northern lineage in Arteaga et al. (2020) whereas the D-loop sequences that we obtained based on shotgun sequencing of the same individuals showed that they mostly belonged to the Southern lineage as expected from their geographical origin (Table S4, Fig. S17). This suggests that the original short D-loop fragment sequences obtained by PCR and Sanger sequencing in Arteaga et al. (2020) might have originated from cross-contamination with other samples of the Northern lineage.

Mito-nuclear phylogenetic discordance and introgression in nine-banded armadillos

We used two complementary approaches to investigate whether introgression could explain the mito-nuclear discordances we recovered (Fig. 1a-b). First, we inferred phylogenetic networks with the nuclear data under a MSC model with introgression using the software SNaQ (Solís-Lemus and Ané 2016) implemented in the package PhyloNetworks (Solís-Lemus et al. 2017). *D. kappleri* was used as an outgroup, and *D. pilosus* was excluded because of its high amount of missing data. Concordance factors were computed in PhyloNetworks from the 832 gene trees previously used in the Astral analysis. SNaQ was then run with maximum numbers of reticulations (hmax) ranging from 0 to 3, with ten independent ML searches for each. This analysis supported the presence of introgression among *D. novemcinctus* lineages (Fig. S9a-b):

introducing one or two reticulations improved the fit of the models compared to a strictly bifurcating tree (average loglik scores of 1.23 and 0.37 vs 2.45, respectively). Even when allowing three reticulations, a maximum of two were recovered. Because the fit of the best models with 1 and 2 reticulations were similar (loglik scores of 0.53 and 0.22, respectively), and increasing the number of parameters in the model might result in overfitting, we considered both as our best models. They recovered the same reticulation, indicating introgression between the ancestors of the Southern lineage and the “west Andes group” (*D. pilosus*, Central and Northern lineages). The major edge of the network supported the Southern lineage as sister to the Guianan lineage (inheritance values $[\gamma] = 0.83$ and 0.75 , respectively). The network with two reticulations additionally supported introgression between Western Mexico populations and the Central lineage, with the major edge supporting the monophyly of the Mexican populations ($\gamma = 0.88$).

To quantify the extent to which these reticulations are supported by our set of gene trees, we used a descriptive approach based on topologies. Because of the low resolution of the gene trees, we used a Topology Weighting (TW) approach to account for non-monophyly of the lineages (Martin and Van Belleghem 2017). We performed TW in two three-taxa sets: 1) Central, Southern and Guianan lineages, (to test for the reticulation in the first network); and 2) Western Mexico (Mexican individuals with Central lineage mitochondrial haplotypes), Eastern Mexico and Central lineages (to test for the additional reticulation in the second network). In each case, we selected gene trees in which all focal individuals were represented (642 and 699 gene trees, respectively), and pruned them to keep the focal lineages and *D. kappleri* as an outgroup, using the ape R package (Paradis and Schliep 2019). TW was run using TWISST (Martin and Van Belleghem 2017). The results were first represented as the distribution of the weights for each of the three possible topologies. Furthermore, we followed Stankowski et al. (2023) and plotted the joint distribution of the three topologies in a ternary diagram using ggtern (Hamilton 2018). We investigated asymmetry in the ternary diagram as a signal of introgression: under neutral processes without gene flow, we expect that the two alternative topologies (i.e., those with the lowest support) would obtain similar weights, similarly to the assumption of the “ABBA-BABA” test (Green et al. 2010; Durand et al. 2011). We quantified asymmetry in the ternary diagrams using the DLR statistic of Stankowski et al. (2023): considering NT1 as the number of trees in the right half of the ternary diagram (i.e., the weight of the first alternative topology is higher than that of the second) and NT2 the number in the left half, then $DLR = \frac{NT1 - (0.5 \times (NT1 + NT2))}{0.5 \times (NT1 + NT2)}$. Significance was assessed using permutation tests with 100,000 permutations. The results of these analyses were concordant with the networks in that the gene tree topologies representing the edges of the network were more common than the alternative discordant topology (Fig. S9c-d). When investigating the position of the Guianan lineage with respect to the Southern and Central lineages, we found little difference between the nuclear and mitochondrial topologies (average weights of 0.37 and 0.35, respectively), while the third topology was slightly less common (average weight of 0.28). Consequently, the joint ternary distribution of the weights was significantly asymmetric towards the mitochondrial topology (DLR = 0.14, p-value = 0.0002). We also found that the gene trees were poorly resolved, with few lending full support (i.e., weight = 1) to any topology. The second analysis, focused on the Northern and Central lineages, recovered a different

pattern. In this case, the nuclear topology (i.e., monophyletic Mexican populations) received high support (average weight of 0.69), while the discordant topologies had similar weights (average weights of 0.15 and 0.16 for the control and mitochondrial topologies, respectively). Nevertheless, we detected a significant asymmetry towards the mitochondrial topology (DLR = 0.20, p-value = 0.0002) but this signal is driven by topologies intermediate between the nuclear and mitochondrial topologies (i.e., in the upper half of the triangle) rather than strongly supporting the mitochondrial topology.

To conclude, these results show that two instances of mito-nuclear discordance are consistent with signals of introgression in the nuclear data. However, the informativeness of our data is limited and the extent to which introgression affects the nuclear data is unclear, particularly in the case of the Western Mexican populations. Moreover, we focused only on two introgression events that coincided with mito-nuclear discordances, but introgression may affect other branches as well. A comprehensive understanding of ancient introgression in the *Dasytus* radiation will necessitate the use of larger genomic datasets (e.g., Whole Genome Sequencing).

Finally, the shifting position of *D. guianensis* between the mitochondrial and nuclear phylogenies may reflect incomplete lineage sorting (ILS) of mitochondrial haplotypes at the root of the radiation. However, we found strong support for the mitochondrial topology in the nuclear gene trees compared to expectations under stochastic coalescent processes (Fig. S9c). This result is in accord with our phylogenetic network analyses (Fig. S9a), which recovered a reticulation between the ancestors of *D. novemcinctus* and the “west Andes group” (*D. pilosus*, *D. fenestratus* and *D. mexicanus*; Fig. S9a). This would be consistent with mitochondrial transfer from the latter into the former at early stages of divergence, leading to the mitochondrial phylogenetic pattern we observed. This scenario would also conform with the biogeographic expectation, as the nuclear topology supports two clades separated by the Central and Northern Andes. Similarly, the presence of numerous *D. fenestratus* mitochondrial haplotypes in Western Mexico (Arteaga et al. 2012, 2020) is unlikely to be explained by ILS, which is not expected to generate geographically consistent patterns (Toews and Brelsford 2012). Accordingly, both gene tree distributions and phylogenetic networks supported introgression between *D. fenestratus* and the Western Mexico populations (Fig. S9). A potential scenario underlying this pattern may have involved a southward expansion of *D. mexicanus* into the range of *D. fenestratus*, with *D. fenestratus* mitochondrial haplotypes persisting locally in *D. mexicanus* populations, as documented in Iberian hares for instance (Melo-Ferreira et al. 2005; Alves et al. 2008). Nevertheless, the power of our data remains limited in terms of introgression detection and further genomic analyses will be needed to understand the phylogeographic history of the *Dasytus* complex.

Table S1: List of biological samples with detailed information on their origin, nature, and use in this study. Samples of *D. novemcinctus* were classified as belonging to Southern, Guianan, Central, and Northern lineages following Hautier et al. (2017) and were colored accordingly.

Samples	Taxon	Origin	Mito	Capture	Voucher	Collecti on date	DNA extraction
DKA-T4339	<i>D. kappleri</i>	French Guiana	X	X	NA	2003	Gibb et al. 2016
DKA-T3365	<i>D. kappleri</i>	French Guiana	X	X	NA	2001	This study
DHY-ZVCM2010*	<i>D. septemcinctus hybridus</i>	Uruguay	X	Excluded	ZVC M2010	1976	Gibb et al. 2016
DSE-T3002	<i>D. septemcinctus septemcinctus</i>	Argentina	X	X	NA	2001	Gibb et al. 2016
DSE-PAP42	<i>D. septemcinctus septemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	NA	1996	This study
DPI-LSUMZ21888*	<i>D. pilosus</i>	Peru	X	X	LSUMZ Mammals 21888	1978	Gibb et al. 2016
DPI-MSB49990*	<i>D. pilosus</i>	Peru	X	X	MSB:Mamm:49990	1980	Gibb et al. 2016
DNO-T4553	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	NA	JAG M5909	2003	This study
DNO-71	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	X	JAG M5361	1995	This study
DNO-T4557	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	X	JAG M5910	2003	This study
DNO-T2863	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	X	JAG M5911	2000	This study
DNO-169	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	NA	JAG M5442	1995	This study
DNO-T1863	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	X	JAG M5912	1997	Gibb et al. 2016
DNO-T1692	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	X	MNHN-ZM-MO- 2000-226	1995	This study
DNO-T2465	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	French Guiana	X	X	MNHN-ZM-MO- 2001-1530	2000	This study
DNO-MC333*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Guyana	X	X	AMNH Mammals 42914	1920	This study#
DNO-AP249	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	IEPA 3102	2006	This study
DNO-AP109	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	Excluded	IEPA 2419	2005	This study
DNO-AP207	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	IEPA 2837	2006	This study
DNO-MC151*	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	HMAM532	2005	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-AJR1	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	NA	2001	This study
DNO-MC88*	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	CNMA 37069	1992	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-MC21*	<i>D. novemcinctus davisii</i>	Mexico	X	X	ENCB-IPN 26577	1986	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-MC176*	<i>D. novemcinctus davisii</i>	Mexico	X	X	NA	2007	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-MC165	<i>D. novemcinctus fenestratus</i>	Costa Rica	X	X	NA	2008	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-MC425*	<i>D. novemcinctus fenestratus</i>	Panama	X	X	USNM Mammals 578437	1990	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-MC393*	<i>D. novemcinctus fenestratus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	USNM Mammals 442790	1968	This study#
DNO-MC323*	<i>D. novemcinctus aequatorialis</i>	Ecuador	X	X	AMNH Mammals 46555	1920	This study#
DNO-MC180*	<i>D. novemcinctus aequatorialis</i>	Ecuador	X	X	NA	2008	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-MC181*	<i>D. novemcinctus aequatorialis</i>	Colombia	X	X	NA	2008	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-PH8*	<i>D. novemcinctus aequatorialis</i>	Colombia	X	X	AMNH Mammals 32356	1911	This study
DNO-MC257*	<i>D. novemcinctus aequatorialis</i>	Colombia	X	X	USNM Mammals 281285	1943	This study#
DNO-NC001821	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	USA	X	X	NA	NA	Arnason et al. (1997)
DNO-MVZ192698	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	USA	X	X	MVZ:Mamm:19269 8	1974	This study
DNO-BM1	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	USA	X	NA	NA	2000	This study
DNO-MC292*	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	NA	2009	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-MC103*	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	Eco-SC-M 980	2000	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-NP276	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	NA	2001	This study
DNO-LS5	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	NA	2000	This study
DNO-MC40*	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	Contam	NA	2007	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-MC58*	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	NA	2003	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-YUC1	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Mexico	X	X	NA	2001	This study
DNO-MC163*	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Guatemala	X	NA	NA	2008	Arteaga et al. 2012
DNO-T2631	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	Belize	X	X	NA	2000	This study
DNO-JP1	<i>D. novemcinctus mexicanus</i>	El Salvador	X	NA	NA	2000	This study

DNO-MC186*	<i>D. novemcinctus davisi</i>	Mexico	Excluded	NA	CNMA 16551	1974	Arteaga et al. 2012
DYE-MLP30.III.90.2	<i>D. mazzai</i>	Argentina	X	X	MLP 30.III.90.2	1988	Gibb et al. 2016
DNO-PH6*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	Excluded	AMNH Mammals 93116	1930	This study
DNO-MC367*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	Excluded	AMNH Mammals 133330	1937	This study#
DNO-AM78	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	IEPA 2560	2008	This study
DNO-MC366*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	AMNH Mammals 133274	1936	This study#
DNO-MC413*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	USNM Mammals 259485	1935	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-PH3*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	AMNH Mammals 133266	1937	This study
DNO-MC355*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	Excluded	AMNH Mammals 91709	1930	This study#
DNO-M275	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Brazil	X	X	INPA SISTAP M275	NA	This study
DNO-MC1000*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Guyana	X	Contam	AMNH Mammals 42441	1919	This study#
DNO-T2360	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Argentina	X	X	NA	2000	This study
DNO-MC327*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Uruguay	X	Excluded	AMNH Mammals 205727	1963	This study#
DNO-T1870	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Paraguay	X	X	NA	1998	This study
DNO-AN1	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Bolivia	X	X	NA	2000	This study
DNO-MC340*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Bolivia	X	X	AMNH Mammals 247662	1980	This study#
DNO-MSB2	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Bolivia	X	X	MSB:Mamm:99077	2000	This study
DNO-MC436*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Bolivia	X	NA	AMNH Mammals 211674	1965	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-MC324*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Ecuador	X	X	AMNH Mammals 67710	1924	This study#
DNO-MC226*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Colombia	X	X	AMNH Mammals 136252	1939	This study#
DNO-MC334*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Peru	X	X	AMNH Mammals 98462	1930	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-MC441*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Peru	X	Excluded	AMNH Mammals 98463	1930	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-NP751	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Peru	X	NA	NA	2002	This study
DNO-MC337*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Peru	X	X	AMNH Mammals 98465	1927	This study#
DNO-MC326*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Trinidad & Tobago	X	X	AMNH Mammals 7549	1894	This study#
DNO-MC401*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	USNM Mammals 442799	1968	This study#
DNO-MC399*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	USNM Mammals 406706	1967	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-MC302*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	AMNH Mammals 144828	1946	This study#
DNO-MC304*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	AMNH Mammals 33151	1906	This study#
DNO-T3380	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	Excluded	NA	2001	This study
DNO-T1921	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	NA	NA	1998	This study
DNO-MC402*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	USNM Mammals 296615	1952	Arteaga et al. 2020
DNO-MC392*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	USNM Mammals 442787	1968	This study#
DNO-MC417*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	X	USNM Mammals 406703	1967	This study#
DNO-MC303*	<i>D. novemcinctus novemcinctus</i>	Venezuela	X	Excluded	AMNH Mammals 78517	1929	This study#
DSA-USNM Mammals372834*	<i>D. sabanicola</i>	Venezuela	X	X	USNM Mammals 372834	1966	Gibb et al. 2016

Notes: Taxon names are based on Wetzel et al. (2008) and Feijó et al. (2018). *: specimens sampled as dried skin pieces. #: museum specimens previously extracted in Arteaga et al. (2012; 2020) and re-extracted for this study. NA: Not Available. AMNH: American Museum of Natural History, New York, USA; CNMA: Colección Nacional de Mamíferos, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, México; Eco-SC-M: Colección Mastozoológica, Colegio de la Frontera Sur, México; ENCB-IPN: Colección Mastozoológica, Instituto Politécnico Nacional, México; HMAM: Colección Mastozoológica Instituto Agropecuario de Hidalgo, México; IEPA: Instituto de Pesquisas Científicas e Tecnológicas do Estado do Amapá, Macapá, Brazil; JAG: collection JAGUARS, ONG Kwata, Institut Pasteur (Cayenne, French Guiana); LSUMZ: Louisiana State University Museum of Natural Science, Baton Rouge, USA; MNHN: Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; MSB: Museum of Southwestern Biology, Albuquerque, USA; MLP: Museo de La Plata, La Plata, Argentina; MVZ: Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, Berkeley, USA; USNM: National Museum of Natural History, Washington, USA; ZVC: Colección de Vertebrados de la Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de la República, Montevideo, Uruguay.

Table S2: Quality statistics a) by locus and b) by individuals after filtering out loci with more than 40% average missing data, for the nine individuals with more than 55% average missing data across loci and the 159 loci with high deviation from Hardy-Weinberg expectation, respectively.

Individuals	Mean depth coverage	Mean missing data	Number of loci
DKA-L2	145.472162	0.01954513523	815
DKA-T4339	128.2827043	0.03373739714	825
DNO-71	164.0646521	0.0188200833	817
DNO-AJR1	74.44794561	0.05845624786	798
DNO-AM78	125.4715846	0.0325786749	818
DNO-AN1	45.84606667	0.1182961862	788
DNO-AP207	172.2518414	0.01379388105	828
DNO-AP249	289.1989869	0.01516992035	830
DNO-FG-L1	248.0977444	0.01088091792	828
Locus	Mean depth coverage	Mean missing data	Number of individuals
Dasytus_novemcinc	154.10323	0.0119297385	60
Dasytus_novemcinc	112.0884	0.03257551459	61
Dasytus_novemcinc	18.28540667	0.3316624	15
Dasytus_novemcinc	162.9911656	0.006787544754	61
Dasytus_novemcinc	152.2060839	0.02568726371	62
Dasytus_novemcinc	50.3231	0.3421326667	3
Dasytus_novemcinc	142.3279717	0.009455048	60
Dasytus_novemcinc	111.2915633	0.0890815195	60

The complete tables are available from the associated Zenodo repository (https://zenodo.org/records/11283950/files/02_Supplementary_tables_%26_figures.zip?download=1)

Table S3: Species delimitation estimated using PHRAPL for the four combinations: i) ((Southern, Guianan), *D. septemcinctus*) ii) ((Southern, Guianan), *D. pilosus*) iii) ((Central, Northern), *D. septemcinctus*) iv) ((Central, Northern), *D. pilosus*). The gdi index has been estimated for the best model (see Fig. S13). This table details the number of simulated genealogies (n), the mean gdi estimation (mean), the lower and upper estimations.

n	mean	lower	upper
((Southern, Guianan), <i>D. septemcinctus</i>)			
10000	0.28	0.26	0.29
((Southern, Guianan), <i>D. pilosus</i>)			
10000	0.18	0.17	0.20
((Central, Northern), <i>D. septemcinctus</i>)			
10000	0.28	0.26	0.29
((Central, Northern), <i>D. pilosus</i>)			
10000	0.32	0.30	0.33

Table S4: Nineteen individuals from Arteaga et al. (2020) were re-extracted and resequenced using shotgun sequencing in our study. The comparison revealed several individuals with a different D-loop sequence. This table details the lineage to which these individuals belong according to Arteaga et al. (2020) and to our mitogenomic results, their sampling locality, and their corresponding haplotype in Arteaga et al. (2020), with the total number of individuals associated with each haplotype in parentheses.

Individuals	Lineage according to Arteaga et al. (2020)	Lineage according to this study	Locality	Haplotype from Arteaga et al. (2020)
MC257	Northern lineage	Central Lineage	Colombia	H54 (26)
MC323	Northern lineage	Central Lineage	Ecuador	Dn33 (1)
MC333	Northern lineage	Guianan Lineage	Guyana	Dn32 (1)
MC326	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Trinidad & Tobago	Dn26 (2)
MC302	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Venezuela	H54 (26)
MC304	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Venezuela	H54 (26)
MC303	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Venezuela	H54 (26)
MC324	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Ecuador	Dn30 (6)
MC367	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Brazil	Dn30 (6)
MC355	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Brazil	Dn35 (4)
MC366	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Brazil	Dn34 (1)
MC327	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Uruguay	Dn35 (4)
MC337	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Peru	Dn36 (2)
MC226	Northern lineage	Southern Lineage	Colombia	Dn30 (6)
MC340	Southern Lineage	Southern Lineage	Bolivia	Dn13 (1)
MC392	Southern Lineage	Southern Lineage	Venezuela	Dn22 (1)
MC401	Southern Lineage	Southern Lineage	Venezuela	Dn21 (1)
MC417	Southern Lineage	Southern Lineage	Venezuela	Dn7 (1)
MC393	Central Lineage	Central Lineage	Venezuela	Dn3 (1)

Table S5: Adult cranial measurements (in millimeters) of the four *Dasypus* species recognized in this study following Feijó & Cordeiro-Estrela (2016). Measurements are given as Mean \pm standard deviation, minimum and maximum values (number of specimens) are based on specimens examined by Feijó et al. (2018).

	<i>D. mexicanus</i>	<i>D. fenestratus</i>	<i>D. guianensis</i>	<i>D. novemcinctus</i>
greatest length of skull	97.91 \pm 3.62, 85.78 - 104.86 (59)	98.46 \pm 6.2, 86.47 - 107.61 (19)	106.40 \pm 7.27, 96.96-128.31 (26)	96.58 \pm 4.92, 81.23 - 108.61 (533)
condylobasal length	89.45 \pm 3.58, 76.64 - 96.30 (59)	89.2 \pm 5.73, 77.54 - 96.41 (19)	98.26 \pm 6.79, 88.74-117.45 (26)	88.68 \pm 4.69, 73.63 - 99.86 (533)
anterior palatal length	21.63 \pm 1.30, 18.74 - 24.62 (59)	22.12 \pm 1.85, 19.12 - 25.6 (19)	23.92 \pm 1.74, 20.54-28.21 (26)	21.81 \pm 1.74, 14.37 - 27.05 (533)
palatal length	64.23 \pm 2.94, 53.37 - 69.78 (59)	63.56 \pm 4.37, 54.41 - 69.68 (19)	71.84 \pm 5.86, 63.78-90.16 (26)	63.95 \pm 3.76, 52.54 - 74.68 (533)
maxilla length	38.10 \pm 2.31, 30.39 - 42.89 (59)	40.99 \pm 3.2, 35.91 - 47.04 (19)	42.39 \pm 4.48, 36.65-54.23 (26)	37.03 \pm 2.67, 26.68 - 44.92 (533)
palatine Length	16.84 \pm 1.47, 13.21 - 19.96 (59)	13.91 \pm 1.75, 10.7 - 17.6 (19)	19.32 \pm 3, 15.33-28 (26)	18.51 \pm 1.93, 11.37 - 25.44 (531)
infraorbital canal length	9.42 \pm 1.24, 6.52 - 12.26 (57)	6.58 \pm 0.84, 5.38 - 8.14 (18)	6.47 \pm 1.05, 3.61-8.40 (26)	7.31 \pm 1.16, 3.18 - 10.49 (531)
maxillary tooththrow length	23.66 \pm 1.60, 19.81 - 27.57 (59)	22.52 \pm 2.34, 16.83 - 25.01 (19)	25.07 \pm 1.90, 22.20-30.88 (26)	23.33 \pm 1.70, 18.25 - 29.12 (533)
nasal length	34.29 \pm 2.29, 26.02 - 38.82 (59)	34.92 \pm 2.71, 28.79 - 38.8 (19)	36.53 \pm 3.11, 30.75-42.70 (26)	31.63 \pm 2.77, 22.86 - 39.03 (529)
lacrimal length	10.64 \pm 1.42, 6.62 - 13.67 (59)	10.3 \pm 1.72, 7.03 - 12.76 (19)	13.03 \pm 1.5, 10.38-17.38 (26)	10.39 \pm 1.27, 7.22 - 14.56 (532)
rostral length	59.93 \pm 2.50, 52.36 - 66.00 (59)	60.64 \pm 4.99, 50.37 - 67.75 (19)	66.32 \pm 5.54, 57.85-82.71 (26)	58.09 \pm 3.78, 47.15 - 68.17 (532)
anteorbital breadth	32.96 \pm 1.58, 29.13 - 37.05 (59)	33.66 \pm 2.38, 29.69 - 38.37 (19)	36.20 \pm 2.39, 30.5-40.61 (26)	32.16 \pm 1.90, 23.43 - 37.98 (533)
palatal breadth	15.31 \pm 0.91, 12.95 - 17.39 (59)	15.47 \pm 2.09, 13.13 - 22.07 (19)	16.12 \pm 2.25, 11.05-20.15 (26)	14.23 \pm 2.18, 8.15 - 18.75 (532)
palatine breadth	13.41 \pm 0.91, 11.43 - 16.21 (59)	14.2 \pm 1.35, 12.02 - 16.98 (19)	15.24 \pm 1.91, 12.24-20.59 (26)	14.56 \pm 0.98, 10.07 - 17.53 (533)
postorbital constriction	23.76 \pm 1.24, 20.77 - 26.53 (59)	24.19 \pm 1.38, 22.12 - 26.42 (19)	25.96 \pm 1.39, 22.76-28.71 (26)	22.90 \pm 1.19, 17.27 - 34.91 (533)
braincase breadth	31.05 \pm 1.73, 28.64 - 41.54 (59)	31.33 \pm 1.69, 28.68 - 34.28 (19)	33.57 \pm 1.76, 30.24-37.99 (26)	31.04 \pm 1.35, 19.32 - 39.1 (533)
zygomatic breadth	41.26 \pm 2.21, 35.58 - 45.69 (59)	41.6 \pm 2.83, 37.15 - 45.41 (19)	44.95 \pm 2.84, 39.86-54.04 (26)	40.55 \pm 2.47, 26.6 - 46.89 (533)
mastoid breadth	27.77 \pm 1.11, 25.05 - 30.86 (59)	28.43 \pm 1.7, 24.57 - 31.62 (19)	29.14 \pm 2.14, 25.86-35.72 (26)	27.32 \pm 1.38, 20.56 - 36.74 (533)
height of jugal bone	6.33 \pm 0.91, 4.97 - 9.36 (59)	7.39 \pm 0.98, 5.61 - 8.78 (19)	8.13 \pm 0.9, 6.21-10.16 (26)	6.64 \pm 0.97, 4.11 - 10.45 (532)
mandible length	77.62 \pm 3.43, 65.71 - 83.49 (59)	77.99 \pm 4.38, 71.29 - 83.93 (18)	84.68 \pm 5.97, 77.23-101.46 (26)	76.43 \pm 4.41, 60.69 - 88.97 (532)
mandibular tooththrow length	25.13 \pm 1.83, 20.97 - 30.35 (59)	24.16 \pm 2.17, 17.48 - 26.4 (19)	26.61 \pm 2.11, 22.04-33.01 (26)	24.82 \pm 1.61, 19.05 - 29.27 (533)

Table S6: Adult external measurements (in millimeters) of the four *Dasypus* species recognized in this study. External and carapace measurements following Feijó et al. (2018). Measurements are given as Mean \pm standard deviation, minimum and maximum values (number of specimens) are based on specimens examined by Feijó et al. (2018).

	<i>D. mexicanus</i>	<i>D. fenestratus</i>	<i>D. guianensis</i>	<i>D. novemcinctus</i>
total length	807.6 \pm 57.1, 680 - 883 (9)	780.4 \pm 64.02, 642 - 850 (10)	859 \pm 56.39, 790 - 945 (5)	733.3 \pm 90.1, 402 - 950 (176)
tail length	385.6 \pm 37.3, 305 - 430 (8)	397.7 \pm 70, 262 - 550 (10)	395.5 \pm 50.74, 339 - 460 (6)	312.6 \pm 66.3, 115 - 450 (170)
hindfoot length	96.7 \pm 19.4, 51 - 120 (9)	81.4 \pm 21.4, 40 - 99 (7)	95 \pm 14.72, 75 - 110 (4)	90.1 \pm 10.9, 44 - 112 (171)
ear length	39.5 \pm 2.4, 35 - 43 (8)	41.8 \pm 2.4, 40 - 45 (6)	49.25 \pm 4.35, 45 - 55 (4)	41.8 \pm 4.6, 20 - 56 (157)
weight (in g):	-	3285.8 \pm 844.5, 2173 - 4256 (5)	6075 \pm 0.67, 5600 - 6500 (2)	4271.7 \pm 1000, 1600 - 6550 (146)
dorsal length of the cephalic shield	97.49 \pm 5.66, 82.75 - 109 (28)	86.94 \pm 10.60, 73.24 - 103 (10)	107.85 \pm 7.58, 95.11 - 116 (6)	95.54 \pm 11.27, 68.92 - 137 (122)
dorsal length of the scapular shield	96.65 \pm 9.41, 75 - 112 (29)	86.6 \pm 11.63, 69 - 110 (15)	88.59 \pm 10.20, 69 - 99 (9)	92.25 \pm 8.76, 69 - 115 (169)
dorsal length of the pelvic shield	131.46 \pm 13.05, 103 - 157 (28)	123.06 \pm 14.22, 105 - 151 (15)	149.57 \pm 13.68, 124 - 168 (7)	133.15 \pm 13.19, 90 - 165 (171)
dorsal length of the caudal sheath with rings	244.04 \pm 22.71, 204 - 284 (23)	243.81 \pm 32.74, 200 - 324 (11)	271 \pm 21.55, 243 - 294 (6)	220.13 \pm 25.82, 164.13 - 287 (111)
dorsal length of the caudal sheath without rings	142.17 \pm 30.57, 97 - 215 (17)	135.28 \pm 22.72, 114 - 172 (7)	150.5 \pm 18.30, 124 - 180 (6)	124.17 \pm 22.09, 59 - 170 (90)

Figure S1: Distribution of 984 targeted nuclear loci (out of the 997 originally targeted) along the chromosome scale assembly of *Dasybus novemcinctus* (mDasNov1.hap2) realized with the R package RIdeogram (Hao et al. 2020).

Figure S2: Mitochondrial genome depth of coverage for the 72 *Dasypus* individuals newly sequenced in this study. The black line corresponds to a 5x depth of coverage.

Figure S3: Calculation of mitochondrial lineage support for detecting contamination. Positions 7, 16, 20 and 25 are diagnostic positions (DP) that distinguish species 1 from species 2. Lineage support is estimated as the product of proportion of DP and read frequency. Individual 1 supports all four DP of species 1 (proportion of DP = 4/4) and each position is supported by all reads (total read frequency = 26/26). In individual 2, reads support the four DP of species 1. However, only three of the four DP support species 2 as the position 16 is excluded (supported by less than three reads). However, DP of species 1 are more strongly supported by reads (total reads frequency (species 1) = 15/26; total reads frequency (species 2) = 9/26). This pattern can be interpreted as cross-contamination. In some cases, reads could support a different haplotype in a DP position (e.g. individual variation, genotyping errors or contamination with something other than the lineages tested), such reads are not recorded, participating to a total lineage support lower than 1.

Figure S4: Mitochondrial lineage support for each individual (see Fig. S3 for the calculation method). Reads supporting synapomorphies of the Northern lineage are in blue, Central lineage in black, Southern lineage in green, Guianan lineage in orange, and *Dasytus pilosus* in red. Reads supporting DP of *D. pilosus* (in red) within individuals of *D. novemcinctus* complex cannot be explained by cross-contamination as DNA extractions and library preparations for these individuals were performed separately from those of the *D. novemcinctus* complex. They can therefore serve as a control for the proportion of shared genotyping errors expected between individuals that have not cross-contaminated each other. Arrows indicate two individuals (DNO-MC1000 and DNO-MC40) suspected to be cross-contaminated.

Figure S5: a) Inbreeding coefficient and b) heterozygosity estimate for individuals according to cleaning steps. Squares correspond to initial data, open circles to data corrected to ensure that heterozygous positions are supported by a proportion of reads between 0.3 and 0.7, and filled circles to final data in which 159 potential paralogous loci were excluded.

Figure S6: Percentage of missing data per captured locus for each *Dasypus* individual. Loci with more than 40% average missing and nine individuals with more than 55% average missing data across loci were excluded based on this analysis.

Figure S7: Summary information of the 837 cleaned nuclear loci representing the number of sequences and the proportion of variable sites according to the percentage of missing data.

Figure S8: Phylogenetic relationships of the 62 *Dasyopus* individuals obtained using Astral on the 832 ML gene trees from the captured nuclear loci reconstructed with IQ-Tree and ModelFinder. Node circles are colored according to the local posterior probabilities (LPP).

Figure S9: Results of analyses to detect introgression. a) Best phylogenetic network inferred with SNaQ, with two reticulations. Number at hybrid edges denote inheritance values (γ). Values at the deepest reticulation indicate γ estimated in the second best (1 reticulation) and best networks, respectively. Major edges are indicated in red and minor edges in blue. b) Likelihood scores of the inferred networks as a function of the number of reticulations. The color and shape of the dots denote the maximum number of reticulations allowed (h_{max}), and the line shows the likelihood score (loglik) of the best model for 0, 1 and 2 reticulations. c-d) Results of topology weighting analyses focusing on the position of the Guianan lineages and the Western Mexico populations, respectively. Top panels show the joint distribution of the weights at the three possible topologies in a ternary diagram. Bottom panels show violin plots of the distribution of each topology individually, with diamonds indicating the average weights.

Figure S10: Cross validation errors according to the number of clusters (K) investigated. The lower the error value, the higher the support for the cluster number.

Figure S11: Detailed analysis of the substructure within the newly recognized *D. novemcinctus* (Southern lineage). a) Distribution and genome composition detailed for all individuals. Outer circles represent mitochondrial lineages and the pie charts represent the assignment probability estimated by the Admixture analysis with $K = 5$. b) PCA of genetic variance conducted on 4182 SNPs for the 24 individuals composing the Southern lineage.

Figure S12: Species delimitation estimated by bPTP-h. The species tree reconstructed using IQ-TREE and ModelFinder from the 837 concatenated nuclear loci illustrates the most supported partition found by bPTP. Clades in red correspond to taxa identified as distinct species by bPTP.

Figure S13: Comparison of the three best models from the model selection estimated with PHRAPL for the four combinations: i) ((Southern, Guianan), *D. pilosus*); ii) ((Southern, Guianan), *D. septemcinctus*); iii) ((Central, Northern), *D. pilosus*); and iv) ((Central, Northern), *D. septemcinctus*). a) best model, b) second best model, and c) third best model. Red arrows represent gene flow. Estimates of migration (m , in red) and split time (t , in black) are detailed. In the left corner AIC, number of K parameters, model rank, $dAIC$ and $wAIC$ are indicated.

Figure S14: Species delimitation estimated using GMYC. a) Number of lineages through time. The red line corresponds to the threshold estimated by GMYC. b) Likelihood profile through time. c) Ultrametric reconstruction of the concatenated sequences of the 837 nuclear loci using IQ-TREE and ModelFinder for each partition. Clades in red represent taxa supported as distinct species by GMYC.

Figure S15: Heatmaps of pairwise genetic indexes between lineages. a) Absolute measure of genetic divergence (Dxy; red) and the net measure of genetic divergence (Da; blue). b) Rate of fixed differences (blue) and the Genomic Differentiation Index (GDI; red).

Figure S16: Effect of filters on admixture results. The graphs represent the proportion of individual loci attributed to one of the four clusters ($K = 4$). Barplots respectively show the results from the admixture analysis performed on all individuals before (lower barplot) and after (upper barplot) filtering the nuclear markers for heterozygous positions not supported by 30% to 70% of the reads and excluding 159 loci with at least 75% of individuals per lineage that were heterozygous for the same position.

Figure S17: Updated map from Arteaga et al. (2020). Colored dots correspond to the lineages as identified in the original study. Gray dots are individuals re-extracted and re-sequenced in our study that were likely misassigned. White dots correspond to individuals from a haplotype that contains at least one individual likely to have been misassigned.

Figure S18: Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of 212 pb of the 16S ribosomal RNA (same as analyzed in Abba et al., (2018)) reconstructed with IQ-Tree. Individuals of *D. hybridus*, *D. guianensis* sp. nov., *D. mazzai*, and *D. sabanicola* are the ones used in their study. Our *D. novemcinctus* individuals from Argentina, Paraguay and Uruguay group with *D. mazzai* and *D. sabanicola* instead of *D. guianensis* as reported in their study.

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